

The Impact of Technology Factors on the Adoption of Digital Marketing in Small Textile Businesses

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Abstract

The study aims to examine the influence of digital marketing technology factors on small textile businesses in Bengaluru. The global textile market growth is anticipated for \$350 billion by 2030, where 76% of B2B buyers performs online research prior making purchase decision. Furthermore, personalized digital interactions of brands are required for 76% consumers. The impact of technology factors on small textile businesses needs to be explored by quantitative approach and 100 small textile businesses in Bengaluru are respondents for the study. The research methodology includes Descriptive Analysis, and Factor analysis.

Keywords: Digital Marketing, Small textile businesses, Technology Factors.

INTRODUCTION

Small Textile Businesses

The textile industry significantly contributes to Indian economy by 2.3% to the gross domestic product, 13% to industrial production, and 12% to exports. The 45 million people are employed by the industry, which is second largest occupation. India ranks second largest global exporter of cotton, jute, silk and handwoven textiles. A business sells garments to customers directly which has an investment and turnover of less than ₹10 Crores is considered for the study.

Digital marketing

Any form of marketing products through online electronic device is referred as digital marketing. As per the Business Standard report published, India has an over 900 million active internet users and leads to second biggest online market in the world. Global digital marketing is quickly evolving, presenting a mix of new trends and statistics which reflects

increasing digital foot print in the country. By 2027, the shift towards digitization result in India's e-commerce market will reach US\$200 billion by gauging social media platforms in reaching and engaging consumers.

Technology factors

Marketing practices are influenced greatly by technological advancements in India. To engage Customers, digital transformation and facilitating innovation strategies. The important factors encompass increased internet penetration, the introduction of digital marketing platforms and the assimilation of technologies. The interplay of strategic marketing practices and technological advancements is transforming the landscape in India, providing business with the tools to effectively navigate the complexities of the digital age and connect authentically with customers.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

(Xu Li 2024) The study includes knowledge management, marketing capability, product innovation, information technology, and competitive advantage variables. The research has developed the conceptual framework wherein to sustain a competitive advantage, a single technological approach is insufficient. In the clothing industry, strengthening business model management of SMEs is crucial, whereas marketing capability, product innovation and information technology can be enabled by strengthening knowledge management of clothing SMEs to achieve competitive advantages. The research has adopted secondary sources of data, related theories, ideas, and literature to arrive at the variables. The study was carried out in Jiangsu, China. The findings of the research provide a possible business model applicable to the clothing industry of SMEs in Jiangsu Province.

(Kumar 2024) The direct influence of digital marketing capabilities and customer relationship management is examined in the research article about the Indian textile industry of small and medium enterprises. The structural equation modeling with partial least squares is the statistical tool applied to primary data collected through the convenient and snowball sampling techniques from business clients. The results of the study exhibit a positive relationship between digital marketing and textile firm performance, with a mediating role of customer relationship management. Search engine optimization, social media, email & content marketing, and data analysis are a broad range skills of digital marketing capabilities. To increase the sales of the firm, performance should enhance the brand visibility, attract new customers and engage them.

(Hanif 2024) The research aims to examine the effect of digital marketing on clothing sales at Tanah Abang Market, Central Jakarta, Indonesia. For the study, a quantitative research method was applied, 403 shop owners were interviewed, and primary data were collected through a survey with a sample size of 162. As per Indonesian data, there is a growing population of internet users and online shoppers, who are potential buyers of the business. The research methodology was descriptive statistics, Linear Regression equation, and ANOVA of SPSS 29. The result of the study concludes that there is a positive and direct effect of digital marketing on an increase in the clothing sales of the shops. An indirect effect to bring potential buyers to increase sales. The utilization of social media, online advertising, and relevant digital content, an increase in sales turnover is experienced by the shop owners.

Objective of the study

The study is to determine the impact of technology factors on the adoption of digital marketing in small textile businesses

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The research method used for the study is structured google form questionnaire followed by data collection and analysis using SPSS. The primary data is collected through Google form questionnaire and 100 respondents, who are small textile businesses are considered for the study. The questionnaire was structured into two parts. The first part has Economic characteristics and second part is the technology factors related statements.

The sample was selected primarily using the convenient sampling and later snowball sampling technique. Respondents were contacted personally

who are interested in the survey. The participants are small textile business in Bengaluru. Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) tool is used for analysis of data. The research methodology includes Descriptive Analysis, and Factor analysis.

Reliability of the study

The result of the study was subject to Cronbach's Alpha test. The resulting statistics reflected alpha value is 0.855 which higher than 0.7 in order to assure reliability of the questionnaire.

INTERPRETATIONS

Business structure

The small textile business are respondents was asked about the business structure that they were in operation. From the below figure number 1, implies that most of the businesses were Sole Proprietorship compressing of 91% and remaining 9% is the Partnership Firm.

Years in operation

The respondents of the study revealed that 81 of them were in operation of the small textile businesses over and above 15 Years, 15 respondents are in operation between 6 to 10 years, 8 of them are in operation of 2 to 5 years, and 3 respondents are performing business less than 1 year.

From the below table number 1, 91 respondents are Sole Proprietorship form of business and 9 respondents are Partnership firm who are in textile and related business with an investment of less than 10 Crores. This implies that both the forms of business organization are the small textile businesses.

Number of Computers

The small textile businesses consist the number of computers in their

business premises. 7% of the respondents had over and above 10 computers, 8% of them had less than 1 computer, 21% of respondents had 2 to 5 computers, where as 64% majority respondents had 6 to 10 computers for their small textile businesses, implies that the businesses have computers for digitalizing their business operation.

Number of Years Connected to the Internet

To indicate the number of years the small textile businesses had internet connection, 4% are less than 1 year had internet connection, 12% had a internet connection over and above 10 years, 18% of the respondents had internet connected for 2 to 5 years, but 66% of the small textile businesses had an internet connection for period of 6 to 10 years, indicates majority businesses had internet connection for these period.

Descriptive Statistics for Technology Factors and the Adoption of Digital Marketing

The responses from small textile businesses on the impact of technology factors on the adoption of digital marketing were tabulated in mean and standard deviation, derived from a Likert scale of 1-5, where; 1 = strongly disagree, 2 = disagree, 3 = neutral, 4 = agree and 5 = strongly agree. The findings of the study imply that small textile businesses agreed that businesses should have stable internet connection, mean = 4.64 and SD = 0.847. The respondents agreed that they prioritize the acquisition of computers, installation of internet and payment of internet bills, mean = 4.50 and SD = 1.029. The businesses are in agreement that they have dedicated computers purposely use of digital marketing mean = 4.30 and SD = 1.178. Lastly, the has business has failed to utilize

digital marketing because of insufficient IT infrastructure mean = 1.85 and SD = 1.42.

Factor Analysis

The Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) measures the sampling adequacy, the KMO measure is 0.765, value greater than 0.05 is accepted. Thereby sampling adequacy is accepted for the study with a tool of factor analysis.

Bartlett's test is another indication of the strength of the relationship among the variables. From the below table that Bartlett's test of Sphericity is significant were the p value is 0.000 which is less than 0.001, which accepts the correlation matrix is not an identity matrix.

A correlation matrix gives the correlation coefficients between a single variable and every other variable in the study. The off-diagonal elements should be less than zero, than the model is good.

The scree plot is a graph of the eigenvalues against all the factors. The graph is useful for determining how many factors to retain. The point of interest is where the curve begins to flatten. From the below it is evident that curve begins to flatten from 3 and 4. Thereby Eigen value above 1 are factors to be retained which are potential that is business has dedicated computers purposely use for digital marketing and the business prioritizes the acquisition of computers, installation of internet and payment of internet bills. The Eigen value below 1 are potential factors but not extracted.

CONCLUSION

The study concludes that there is significant relationship between technology factor and the adoption of digital marketing. Information technology infrastructure play a pivot role in increasing the awareness and usage of the adoption of digital

marketing in the business. The research highlights the internet connectivity infrastructure is essential in supporting the operations of digital marketing devices in the process of adoption of digital marketing.

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Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	Cronbach's Alpha Based on Standardized Items	N of Items
.855	.865	3

Table Number 1: Cross tabulation of Business structure and Business Investment

Business Structure * Business Investment Cross tabulation			
		Business Investment	Total
		Less than 10 Crores	
Business Structure	Sole Proprietorship	91	91
	Partnership	9	9
Total		100	100

Table Number 2: Descriptive Statistics for Technology Factors

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
Business has dedicated computers purposely use for digital marketing	100	4.3800	1.17877
The business prioritizes the acquisition of computers, installation	100	4.5000	1.02986
The business has a stable internet connection	100	4.6400	.84710
Business has failed to utilize digital online marketing	100	1.8500	1.42400
Valid N (listwise)	100		

Table Number 3: KMO and Bartlett's Test

KMO and Bartlett's Test

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.		.765
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	152.226
	df	6
	Sig.	.000

Table Number 4: Correlation Matrix

		Business has dedicated computers purposely use for digital marketing	The business prioritizes the acquisition of computers, installation	The business has a stable internet connection	Business has failed to utilize digital online marketing
Sig. (1-tailed)	Business has dedicated computers purposely use for digital marketing		.000	.000	.001
	The business prioritizes the acquisition of computers, installation	.000		.000	.000
	The business has a stable internet connection	.000	.000		.004
	Business has failed to utilize digital online marketing	.001	.000	.004	

Figure Number 1: Business structure

Figure Number 2: Years in operation

Figure Number 3: Number of Computers

Figure Number 4: Number of Years Connected to the Internet

Figure Number 5: Scree Plot

